

Synthesis of polyesters with azomethine groups in the polymer backbone

A. Muthusamy, S. Karthikeyan, K. Ramarajan and L. Ravikumar*

Department of Chemistry, C. B. M. College, Kovaipudur, Coimbatore-641 042, India

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Polyesters containing one and two azomethine as well as -O-, -CH₂- linking groups between phenylene rings with terephthalic, isophthalic and adipic acids have been prepared. Their thermal stability has been studied. Some of them have thermotropic liquid crystal properties.

When rigid, rod-shaped molecules (mesogens) are present as a part of the polymer backbone, it is anticipated to give liquid crystal behaviour¹. Owing to the very high melting point the aromatic backbone are segmented with spacers. The spacer is usually a sequence of methylene units. Moreover, when chromophoric groups such as azo, azomethine are present in such polymers, they influence the thermal and liquid crystalline behavior^{2,3}. In continuation of our earlier report⁴, we report here the synthesis and thermal stability of new polyesters with azomethine groups by reacting the dihydroxy monomers containing azomethine groups with aliphatic and aromatic diacid chlorides. There are only a few reports about the polymers with azomethine groups as mesogens. The azomethine polymers derived from aliphatic diacid chlorides are expected to show liquid crystalline properties. Those derived from aromatic diacid chlorides do not melt before degradation. Hence, their liquid crystalline properties can not be assessed.

Results and Discussion

The structures of bisphenols (Scheme 1) were confirmed by IR and electronic spectral data.

The UV spectra of monomer **3** and polymer **3** + ISO show λ_{max} at 438 and 411.5 nm, respectively, corresponding to $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi$ transition. The IR spectra contain C=N stretch at 1610–1630 cm^{-1} . A sharp band at about 3500 cm^{-1} of monomer **4** is due to stretching vibrations of OH group. A sharp peak at 1735–1740 cm^{-1} of polymers **5** + TER, **5** + ISO and **4** + TER is due to the ester link⁵ in the polymer which is not observed in the monomer.

The inherent viscosity and solubility data are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 reveals that the yield and the molecular weight are high for the polyesters obtained from bisphenols **4** and **5** than those from other three bisphenols. Bisphenols,

Scheme 1

which contain electron-attracting substituents, do not enter into polycondensation as readily as unsubstituted or electron-releasing substituted bisphenols⁶. In the present case of bisphenols **1-3**, the electron-withdrawing effect of the azomethine group increases the acidity of phenol and thereby decreasing the basic strength of phenoxide ion during interfacial polycondensation. Such effect is less with bisphenols **4** and **5** and hence the higher yield and molecular weight. All the polyesters are soluble in conc. H₂SO₄, and the polyesters obtained from aromatic acid chlorides are partially soluble in *o*-chlorophenol. However, polyesters obtained from aliphatic diacids are soluble in all the three solvents.

The TG curves of the polyazomethine esters from terephthaloyl chloride, isophthaloyl chloride and adipoyl chloride were recorded. The temperatures corresponding to 10 and 20% weight-loss of the polymers on thermal degradation

Table 1. Properties of polymers

Polymer	Yield %	η_{inh} dl g ⁻¹	Solubility*	
			Dimethyl formamide	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol
1 + TER	74.1	0.13	+-	+-
2 + TER	61.0	0.15	--	--
3 + TER	64.7	0.11	--	+-
4 + TER	91.0	0.83	--	+-
5 + TER	73.0	0.72	--	+-
1 + ISO	30.7	0.22	+-	+-
2 + ISO	44.0	0.15	--	+-
3 + ISO	84.9	0.25	--	+-
4 + ISO	82.0	0.77	--	+-
5 + ISO	92.0	0.71	--	+-
1 + ADI	33.9	0.27	++	++
2 + ADI	46.9	0.22	++	++
3 + ADI	67.6	0.27	++	++
4 + ADI	51.0	0.67	++	++
5 + ADI	62.0	0.61	++	++

*(++ = Soluble, (+-) = partially soluble, (--) = insoluble; all polymers are soluble in conc. H₂SO₄.

and the type of mesophase texture noticed on melting are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. TG data for the polyesters*

Polymer	<i>T</i> _{10%}	<i>T</i> _{20%}	Mesophase texture
	°C	°C	
1 + TER	324	424	-
2 + TER	324	460	-
3 + TER	460	500	-
4 + TER	440	512	-
5 + TER	444	484	-
1 + ISO	336	392	-
2 + ISO	312	404	-
3 + ISO	424	472	-
4 + ISO	466	532	-
5 + ISO	356	440	-
1 + ADI	232	312	-
2 + ADI	216	284	Weak nematic schlieren
3 + ADI	300	432	Strong nematic schlieren
4 + ADI	348	432	Faint nematic schlieren
5 + ADI	372	396	-

**T*_{10%} = Temperature of 10% weight-loss; *T*_{20%} = temperature of 20% weight-loss.

Thermogravimetric analysis indicates that, for fully aromatic polyesters, the terephthalic and isophthalic polyesters have higher thermal stability than the polyesters derived from the aliphatic acid chlorides. Among the aromatic azomethine polyesters, due to the higher stability of ester group attached to aromatic ring⁷ as well as the aromatic azomethine group, the probable chain scission is at the bridge between phenylene rings. For 20% degradation, the order of stability for polyesters 4 + TER and 5 + TER as well as 4 + ISO and 5 + ISO is found to be

which is anticipated for the series⁸ -(C₆H₄-X)_n, where, X = -, O, CH₂. In the present case, for 20% degradation polyazomethine esters obtained from aromatic acids are found to have the following order of stability :

The thermal stability of terephthalic polyesters is slightly higher than the isophthalic polyesters. However, polyazomethine esters from the aliphatic acid show a different type of thermal stability because degradation in their cases leads to ester scission⁹. Taking into consideration the structure of bisphenols, it may be observed that the polyesters from the bisphenol 3 exhibit a higher thermal stability which is comparable to that of the polyesters derived from bisphenol 4. Terephthalic and isophthalic polyesters do not melt before decomposition.

Some of the polyesters derived from bisphenols 2, 3 and 4 with aliphatic acid chloride exhibit thermotropic liquid crystalline properties. On melting and when observed with a polarizing microscope, the solid melts of the polyesters 2 + ADI, 3 + ADI and 4 + ADI show nematic schlieren texture⁹.

Experimental

4-Aminophenol (B.D.H.), vanillin (Ranbaxy), 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (Sigma), 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ether (Fluka), 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (Fluka) and terephthalaldehyde (Fluka) were all recrystallised from ethanol. Terephthaloyl chloride, isophthaloyl chloride, and adipoyl chloride were prepared from the respective diacids. For the preparation of bisphenols, the aminophenols were condensed with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and terephthalaldehyde. The diamines were condensed with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde. The polyesters were synthesized by interfacial polycondensation method⁴.

Solubility tests were carried out in conc. H₂SO₄, *o*-chlorophenol and DMF. Viscosity was measured in an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer at 30° in conc. H₂SO₄ (98%). Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hitachi U2000 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 273 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The TG curves for the polymers were recorded in STA1500 PL V4-30 and V4 IC DuPont2000 instruments in nitrogen atmosphere in the temperature range 100–600° at a heating rate of 20° min⁻¹.

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